

Adsorption of Ions and of Sols at Interfaces and its Applications to certain Problems of Colloid Chemistry.

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Experiments on the adsorption of various electrolytes by sols as well as by freshly precipitated substances have been carried on in these laboratories for more than ten years. As adsorbents we have used hydrated manganese dioxide, ferric hydroxide, aluminium hydroxide, chromium hydroxide, stannic hydroxide, vanadium pentoxide, silicic acid, arsenious sulphide, antimony sulphide, barium sulphate, etc. In this communication I shall briefly state the important results obtained by us.¹

We have observed that hydrated manganese dioxide mainly adsorbs the basic portions of salts making the neutral solutions acid after adsorption. Similarly barium sulphate in the course of its formation mainly adsorbs the acid radicles from neutral salts making the solutions distinctly alkaline.

From the experimental results on adsorption, which are available at present, we have come to the following conclusions:—

(1) The generally accepted view that an ion, which is highly adsorbed also possesses a high coagulating power is not supported by experiments on adsorption.

(2) There is no justification for the assumption that the greater the valency and hence the coagulating power of an ion, the greater is its adsorption.

(3) On the other hand, experiments on the coagulation and adsorption of different ions by sols of HgS , Sb_2S_3 , $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, V_2O_5 , MnO_2 , etc., strongly support our view that the greater the valency of an ion, the less is the amount of adsorption.

¹ *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 121, 135; 1923, 152, 399, 405; *Jour. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, 26, 701, 836; 1923, 27, 376; 1924, 28, 313, 457; 1925, 29, 435, 659; 1926, 30, 628, 880; *Koll. Zeit.*, 1923, 33, 18, 29, 193; 1924, 34, 262; 1924, 35, 144; 1925, 36, 129.

(4) It has been shown that the large amount of adsorption of ions associated with the coagulation of sols like MnO_2 , $Fe(OH)_3$, $Al(OH)_3$, $Cr(OH)_3$, etc., is mainly due to the marked chemical affinity of these substances for the coagulating ions.

It is of interest to note that those substances, which can form complex salts with the adsorbent are adsorbed most.

It appears that hydrated MnO_2 , which behaves like H_2MnO_4 , and hydrated SiO_2 , which behaves like H_2SiO_4 , can adsorb large quantities of OH' ions, because an acidic substance has naturally a great affinity for OH' ions.

It has been proved (Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 125) that when an alcoholic solution of iodine is added to starch sol, the electric conductivity of the blue substance formed is much greater than the sum of the conductivities of the individual substances. The product obtained by the adsorption of iodine by starch is appreciably conducting and behaves something like an unstable iodide.

It will be interesting to mention here that Gillespie and Hall (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 1207) and Lambert and Gates (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, A 108, 456) have concluded from their experiments on the adsorption of hydrogen by palladium that definite chemical combination takes place between hydrogen and palladium.

We have observed a peculiar phenomenon, that the adsorption of ions by MnO_2 depends on the total volume of the solution used and for a definite concentration of the electrolyte, increase in the volume of the electrolyte leads to an increment in the amount of adsorption by a definite weight of MnO_2 , showing that the simple adsorption isotherm is not obtained with the adsorption by MnO_2 .

Evidently the phenomenon of adsorption is most marked when there is chemical affinity between the adsorbent and the substance which is being adsorbed.

Adsorption of ions carrying the same charge as the sol or the suspended solid substance.

We have proved that negatively charged hydrated manganese dioxide, not only adsorbs cations but it also adsorbs appreciable quantities of anions and of OH' ions.

The following results were obtained in the adsorption of acids and bases by hydrated manganese dioxide:—

Electrolyte.	Original concentration of H ⁺ or OH ⁻ ion.	Amount of H ⁺ or OH ⁻ ion adsorbed.
H ₂ SO ₄ .	0·0094 gr. of H ⁺	0·0003 gr. H ⁺
CH ₃ CO ₂ H	0·0162 „ „	0·0003 gr. H ⁺
NaOH	0·0170 gr. of OH ⁻	0·008 gr. OH ⁻
KOH	0·0170 gr. of OH ⁻	0·008 gr. OH ⁻

The following results were obtained with hydrated silica:—

Electrolyte.	Original concentration.	Percentage of adsorption.
CH ₃ CO ₂ H	0·0540	0·46
H ₂ C ₂ O ₄ .	0·0910	0·26
C ₆ H ₅ CO ₂ H	0·0145	0·24
H ₂ SO ₄ .	0·0266	0·51
HCl	0·0298	0·12
HNO ₃	0·0322	0·21
NH ₄ OH	0·00351	29·1
NaOH	0·00564	30·68
Ca(OH) ₂	0·00059	77·27
Ba(OH) ₂	0·00768	54·4

The foregoing experiments prove that though hydrated MnO₂ or SiO₂ is negatively charged, more of OH⁻ ions are adsorbed than H⁺ ions, because of the marked chemical affinity of the acidic substances like MnO₂, SiO₂ etc., for OH⁻ ions. Here we see that adsorption is influenced more by chemical affinity of the adsorbent for the substance which is being adsorbed than the nature of the electric charge on the adsorbent.

We have also proved that barium sulphate in the course of its precipitation, not only adsorbs negative ions from electrolytes, but it also adsorbs positive ions as the following results will show.

Electrolyte.	Original concentration of positive ion.	Percentage of adsorption.
KCl	0·1038 M	0·1
K ₂ C ₂ O ₄ .	0·06894 M	2·0
KBrO ₃	0·09400 M	0·6
Na ₂ AsO ₄	0·06888 M	3·7

We have also observed that Cl⁻, SO₄⁻² and C₂O₄⁻² ions are adsorbed by negatively charged sols of As₂S₃, Sb₂S₃ etc., when they are

coagulated by KCl, K_2SO_4 , $K_2C_2O_4$, etc. The following quantitative result has been obtained with KCl and As_2S_3 sol:—

Adsorption of Potassium and Chlorine Ions.

Amount of As_2S_3 = 0.4508 gram; volume = 100 c.c.

Original concentration.	Final concentration.	Adsorption.
0.05997 Cl'	0.05900 Cl'	1.6 per cent.
0.05997 K°	0.05790 K°	3.3 ..

Hence the ratio of the adsorption of potassium ion to chlorine ion in the coagulation of a sol of As_2S_3 by KCl is 2.06.

The importance of the adsorption of ions carrying the same charge as the sol will be evident from the following considerations:—

(1) The abnormal dilution effect, shown by sols like As_2S_3 , Sb_2S_3 , S_2 , mastic, gum dammar, Prussian blue etc., when coagulated by univalent ions like K^+ , Na^+ , Li^+ etc., (*viz.* more of electrolytes like KCl, NaCl, LiCl etc., are necessary to coagulate a dilute sol than a concentrated one), is mainly due to the fact that these sols can adsorb ions carrying the same charge as the sols.

(2) The abnormal behaviour, shown by sols like As_2S_3 , Sb_2S_3 , mastic, Prussian blue, etc., when coagulated by mixtures of electrolytes (*i.e.* the precipitation values of mixtures of electrolytes of widely varying precipitating powers are much greater than the additive values), is also due to the adsorption of ions carrying the same charge as the sol.

(3) The phenomenon of positive acclimatization has been explained from the point of view that colloidal particles can adsorb ions carrying the same charge as the sol. It follows, therefore, that such sols as As_2S_3 , Sb_2S_3 , mastic, etc., which are known to adsorb negative ions show this phenomenon more markedly than sols of $Fe(OH)_3$, $Cr(OH)_3$, etc., which hardly adsorb monovalent ions carrying the same charge as the sols.

(4) Moreover, we have proved that when small quantities of electrolytes insufficient to coagulate the sols are added to them, the sols adsorb ions carrying the same charge as the sol and their stability is increased due to the increase in their charge and the viscosity is slightly decreased.

Consequently we are of the opinion that the above four phenomena,—(a) abnormality of sols to follow the general dilution rule,

(b) the abnormal behaviour of sols towards a mixture of electrolytes of widely varying precipitating powers, (c) the phenomenon of positive acclimatization and (d) the decrease of viscosity of sols on the addition of small quantities of electrolytes, are essentially connected and go hand in hand and are mainly due to the adsorption of ions carrying the same charge as the sol. We have observed that the above generalisation is applicable to sols of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ (negatively charged and positively charged), $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ (negatively charged and positively charged), $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, MnO_2 (negative and positive), $\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_2$ (negative and positive), Prussian blue, uranium ferrocyanide, thorium hydroxide, mastic, gum dammar, As_2S_3 , Sb_2S_3 , sulphur, gold, silver, V_2O_5 etc. Moreover we have proved that when positively charged ferric hydroxide is coagulated by KCl , K_2SO_4 , K_2HPO_4 etc., no abnormality is obtained, but when the above sol is coagulated by FeCl_3 or $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, the sol behaves abnormally towards dilution, towards a mixture of electrolytes, shows the phenomenon of positive acclimatization markedly and shows decrease of viscosity on the addition of small quantities of FeCl_3 (compare the measurements of Thomas and Frieden, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 2522, on the viscosity of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ sol in presence of FeCl_3); because Fe^{+++} or Al^{+++} ions are adsorbed by a positively charged sol of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$.

Experimental results on the viscosity measurements of colloids, specially of the hydrophobe type, are in support of the following assumptions:—

(1) Other things being equal, the uncharged substance is more hydrated than the sol.

(2) The greater the hydration of a substance, the greater is its viscosity.

(3) When a sol adsorbs an ion carrying the same charge as the sol due to chemical affinity and thus the charge on the sol is increased, we always observe a decrease in the viscosity of the sol.

(4) When the sol adsorbs more of the ion carrying the opposite charge than the ion carrying the same charge, the charge on the sol is decreased and more of hydration will take place and the viscosity will be increased (compare Dhar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 129, 1556; *Zeit. Elektrochem.*, 1925, 31, 261; Chakravarti and Dhar, *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 162, 393).

Our experimental results on the viscosity of various sols in presence of small quantities of electrolytes are in opposition to the view that the sol is more hydrated than the coagulated

mass and that greater the charge on a particle, the greater the hydration.

Adsorption of Sols by their own Precipitates.

We have made quantitative experiments on the adsorption of sols by their own freshly obtained precipitates, free from all electrolytes. We have observed that many sols are copiously adsorbed by the solid precipitates of the same substances.

(a) Adsorption of a sol of silver chromate by freshly precipitated silver chromate.

A sol of silver chromate was prepared by adding a dilute solution of silver nitrate to an equivalent amount of potassium chromate containing gelatine.

Solid silver chromate was obtained by the interaction of silver nitrate and potassium chromate and was thoroughly washed free from electrolytes. The solid silver chromate was suspended in water and known amounts were taken out by means of a pipette after thoroughly shaking the water containing the precipitate. One typical experimental result is given below:—

Weight of Ag_2CrO_4 in 10 c.c. water containing Ag_2CrO_4	= 1.4680 g.
Weight of Ag_2CrO_4 in 25 c.c. sol	= 0.0141 g.
Concentration of gelatine in the sol	= 0.25%

Ratio of $\frac{\text{Ag}_2\text{CrO}_4 \text{ precipitate}}{\text{Sol}}$ by weight	Percentage of adsorption.
26	32.3
52	43.1
78	56.1
104	66.5
156	73.6
208	81.7
312	90.6

Similar experiments were carried on the adsorption of a sol of PbCrO_4 by a precipitate of lead chromate. The sol of lead chromate was obtained by the action of lead acetate on potassium chromate containing agar.

Concentration of agar in the sol = 0.238%

Weight of lead chromate in 10 c.c. of water containing PbCrO_4 = 0.7058 g.

Weight of PbCrO_4 per litre of sol = 0.3096 g.

Ratio of $\frac{\text{Precipitate}}{\text{sol}}$ by weight	Percentage of adsorption.
22.8	63.4
30.4	71.0
45.6	73.0
60.8	74.1
68.4	85.0
91.2	87.0
182.4	89.0

The foregoing experimental results prove that sols of silver chromate, lead chromate, etc., are markedly adsorbed by their solid precipitates. Similarly we have found out that sols of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$, HgO , ZnS , As_2S_3 , etc., are adsorbed by their solid precipitates.

On the other hand, sols of Sb_2S_3 , CdS , Ag_2S , In_2O_3 , etc., are not adsorbed by their respective solids.

Basing on these experiments we have advanced a theory of the formation of Liesegang rings (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 41; *Koll. Zeit.*, 1924, 35, 270; 1925, 37, 2, 89). The basic idea of our theory is that Liesegang rings are formed by the coagulation of a peptised sol and that the coagulated mass in the course of its coagulation and when coagulated adsorbs and coagulates completely or partially the sol of the same substance from the neighbouring layers.

If the precipitate is unable to adsorb and coagulate the sol, there would not be any clear space, but bands consisting of alternate layers of different colours will form.

We have proved that there are two distinct classes of Liesegang rings. In one class, two consecutive rings are separated by clear spaces, whilst in the other case, the rings consist of a layer of coagulated sol followed by a layer of the peptised substance.

The theory advanced by us takes into consideration the influence of the gel and assumes that the sparingly soluble substance, e.g., silver chromate formed by diffusing silver nitrate into potassium chromate in gelatine gel, is at first in the colloidal condition due to the peptising influence of the gel. Owing to the high concentration of the diffusing electrolyte at the beginning, the quantity of the sparingly soluble substance formed is much in excess to that which the gel can hold in suspension and thus it coagulates, this process being further facilitated by the other product of the chemical change

(*e.g.*, KNO_3 in this case). The advancing layers of the diffusing electrolyte (*e.g.*, AgNO_3) meet fresh quantity of potassium chromate and produce silver chromate at first in the colloidal condition. This sol of silver chromate is gradually adsorbed and coagulated by the solid silver chromate already formed. In this way, a layer next to the solid becomes free from silver chromate sol which removes along with it the chromate ions used in its production. The diffusing silver nitrate passes through this layer, which is practically free from chromate ions and comes in contact with another layer of potassium chromate and at first it forms a layer of colloidal silver chromate, which can no longer be adsorbed and coagulated by the solid silver chromate already formed, as the limit of adsorption has been already reached and this new layer is formed a little too far from the solid silver chromate for the possibility of its being adsorbed by the solid silver chromate. Now the silver nitrate is continually diffusing and gradually the concentration of the silver chromate sol increases and finally the limit to which the gel can hold the silver chromate in suspension is reached and the silver chromate becomes coagulated. The process repeats itself and we get a series of rings separated by clear spaces practically free from the sparingly soluble substance.

We have proved that a stable yellow negatively charged sol of silver chromate is formed in gelatine by the preferential adsorption of chromate ions, whilst a red unstable sol of positively charged silver chromate is formed by the adsorption of silver ions.

Moreover, our theory is capable of predicting that those freshly obtained precipitates, which are capable of adsorbing their respective sols will form Liesegang rings of the first type in which two consecutive rings will be separated by a clear space, whilst substances which cannot adsorb their respective sols should give Liesegang rings of the second type, which consists of alternate layers of different colours. Experimental results show that Ag_2CrO_4 , PbCrO_4 , $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ etc., which can adsorb their respective sols form Liesegang rings of the first type, whilst Sb_2S_3 , CdS , MnO_2 etc., which cannot adsorb their own sols, form Liesegang rings of the second type in which there are no clear spaces.

We have been able to prove from experiments that our theory stands on a better footing than the theories of Wilhelm Ostwald (*Zeit. physikal Chem.*, 1897, 23, 365) Bradford (*Biochem. J.*, 1916, 10, 169; 1917, 14, 157) and Wolfgang Ostwald (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1925, 36, 380).

Summary and Conclusion

(1) Experiments on the adsorption of ions by sols of HgS , Sb_2S_3 , $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, V_2O_5 , MnO_2 , etc., show that the greater the valency of an ion, the less is the amount of adsorption. There is no experimental support for the assumption that the greater the valency and hence the coagulating power of an ion, the greater is its adsorption.

(2) The phenomenon of adsorption is most marked when there is chemical affinity between the adsorbent and the substance which is being adsorbed.

(3) Experimental results show that sols are capable of adsorbing ions carrying the same charge as the sol.

(4) The abnormality of sols to follow the general dilution rule, the abnormal behaviour of sols towards a mixture of electrolytes, the phenomenon of positive acclimatization and the decrease of viscosity of sols on the addition of small quantities of electrolytes, are essentially connected and are mainly due to the adsorption of ions carrying the same charge as the sol.

(5) Experiments on viscosity of sols in presence of electrolytes show that other things being identical, an increase in the charge of the sol produces a decrease in the viscosity and hydration of the sol.

(6) Sols of silver chromate, lead chromate, ferric hydroxide, etc., are copiously adsorbed by their respective solids. On the other hand, sols of antimony sulphide, cadmium sulphide, manganese dioxide etc., are not adsorbed by their solid substances. Basing on these observations, a theory of the formation of Liesegang rings in which a layer of precipitate is followed by a clear space, has been advanced.

